

Opinion Paper

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Navigating the path of reproducibility in microRNA-based biomarker research with ring trials

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Abstract: The development of microRNA (miRNA)-based biomarkers has gained significant attention due to their potential diagnostic, prognostic and therapeutic applications. However, the reproducibility of miRNA biomarker research faces unique challenges, primarily due to the influence of pre-analytical and analytical factors. The absence of standardized procedures contributes to inconsistencies across studies, alongside challenges in reference gene selection, data analysis methods and miRNA profiling platforms. Inter-laboratory comparison trials, or ring trials, offer a strategic approach to address technical and biological variability in miRNA biomarker studies. These trials promote standardization, identify sources of variability and strengthen the correlation between miRNAs and clinical outcomes. Despite their underutilization in miRNA biomarker research, ring trials represent a valuable tool for enhancing reproducibility and expediting the translation of miRNA-based biomarkers into clinical applications.

Keywords: biomarker; microRNA; ring trial

Reproducibility of microRNA-based biomarkers

The development of microRNA (miRNA)-based biomarkers has attracted significant attention due to their potential diagnostic, prognostic and therapeutic applications [1]. However, as the field expands, concerns about result reliability have become increasingly pronounced.

Reproducibility in miRNA biomarker research presents unique challenges, primarily due to the substantial impact of external factors (reviewed in detail in [2]). The variations in sample processing, e.g., timing for blood sampling, centrifugation protocol or sample storage, among others, coupled with the absence of standardized procedures, contribute to inconsistencies across studies. Furthermore, challenges arise from the selection of reference genes, diverse data analysis methods and the use of different platforms for miRNA profiling [3].

It is critical to explore and quantify the sources of variation across various laboratories within the analytical, analytical and post-analytical pipelines. Beyond internal quality controls, external ring trials, a practice well-established in the optimization of molecular markers, have proven to be invaluable tools for achieving the required quality standards [4, 5].

Ring trials for microRNA-based biomarker research

In the routine laboratory practice, external quality controls play a pivotal role in evaluating the performance of individual laboratories to measure biomarkers currently used in the clinic. These controls are essential for ensuring the accuracy and reliability of measurements, thereby maintaining high standards of patient care. However, the current absence of such standardized materials specifically tailored for miRNA quantification presents a significant challenge and may delay

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their future clinical application. This gap necessitates the adoption of alternative strategies that can effectively assess and enhance laboratory performance.

Inter-laboratory comparison trials, or ring trials, offer a strategic approach to address both technical and biological variability in miRNA biomarker studies. In these trials, homogeneous samples are distributed to various independent laboratories, which analyze the same sample or set of samples using standard methods and procedures under control of a supervising laboratory (as illustrated in Figure 1). The

results obtained by each laboratory are then compared to assess the agreement among them.

One primary advantage of ring trials for miRNA biomarker development is the promotion of standardization. Evaluating the consistency and reproducibility of results from different laboratories helps identify potential sources of variability or bias, leading to the formulation of consensus protocols for sample handling, quantification and data analysis. By pinpointing these sources of variability, researchers can implement corrective measures and adopt

Figure 1: Ring trial phases for microRNA-based biomarker research (created with BioRender.com).

best practices, thereby providing a way for the harmonization of assay protocols [6]. Moreover, outcomes from ring trials can provide guidance to newly established laboratories implementing protocols, aiding them in adopting best practices.

In addition to addressing technical variability, ring trials are crucial for introducing novel biomarkers into clinical settings [7]. Consistent findings across multiple laboratories enhance confidence in potential candidates, reinforcing their translation. This not only could facilitate the validation of specific miRNAs or miRNA signatures but also strengthens the association between miRNAs and clinical outcomes. The subsequent phase may involve initiating a clinical trial employing the methods validated.

Ring trials stimulate the collaboration among researchers, clinicians and industry stakeholders. The shared goal of improving reproducibility encourages research groups to exchange information. Collaborative efforts lead to the establishment of guidelines and recommendations, further promoting standardized practices.

Unexpectedly, despite the proven efficacy of ring trials in studies involving other biomarkers, their adoption in the field of miRNA-based biomarkers has been notably limited.

Considerations and challenges

Ring trials are indispensable for reducing variability across laboratories, but the efficacy of these trials depends heavily on their design and the specificity of questions they aim to answer. To address the challenges posed by the inherent variability in miRNA quantification and the absence of standardized materials, a meticulously planned ring trial is essential. It must aim to unequivocally identify which variables most significantly influence the variability of results.

The cornerstone of a successful ring trial is the establishment of a collaborative framework among participants. This involves synchronizing methodologies and reaching a consensus on the optimal practices for each step subject to validation. To ensure a comprehensive evaluation, the trial must include detailed protocols on various aspects, including but not limited to:

- 1) Specifying the type of primary sample to standardize the starting material across studies;
- 2) Standardizing the brand and volume of tubes for blood collection to minimize pre-analytical variability;
- 3) Establishing a timeline for blood draw to processing, setting clear benchmarks for timing to ensure consistency;
- 4) Defining precise blood processing conditions, including centrifugation speed, duration and temperature, to standardize sample preparation;

- 5) Agreeing on storage conditions to preserve sample integrity over time;
- 6) Choosing an RNA extraction method and determining the starting volume of material to ensure comparability;
- 7) Defining the specific spike-ins to be added during the extraction phase to monitor extraction efficiency and quantify recovery rates;
- 8) Adjusting original extraction protocols if needed to accommodate the specific requirements of the ring trial, ensuring clarity on any deviations;
- 9) Detailing the quantification and quality control methodologies to assess RNA purity and concentration accurately;
- 10) Specifying the reverse transcription protocol, including reagent brands, spike-in controls and volumes, to standardize cDNA synthesis;
- 11) Outlining the qPCR protocol, including reagent brands and controls, to ensure reliability and reproducibility of amplification results;
- 12) Establishing a standardized approach for data normalization and result reporting to facilitate comparative analysis and interpretation.

Upon reaching consensus on these critical details, the focus shifts to delineating the ring trial's scope and the specific steps for validation. Ideally, all steps would undergo validation, yet this ambition may be overly ambitious in the trial's initial stages. A practical solution is to nominate a central laboratory equipped to collect and process samples, then prepare additional aliquots at every stage. This setup enables other participating laboratories to engage in the experiment from any given point. Such a strategy allows for the validation of various steps' variability across laboratories, tailored to the trial's objectives. This phased approach ensures a manageable complexity level while still achieving comprehensive validation across pivotal stages.

While interlaboratory ring trials offer substantial benefits, they are not without challenges. For instance, the limited number of participating laboratories may introduce a selection bias and affect the generalizability of results. Additionally, the choice of sample type, known to significantly influence miRNA quantification [2], may not fully represent the diverse matrix found in clinical laboratories, potentially leading to an underestimation of method performance. Variability can be introduced at various stages of the trial, including sample collection, preparation, storage and shipment, miRNA quantification, data analysis and results interpretation. Ensuring the homogeneity of distributed samples, rigorous quality control measures and establishing a comprehensive framework for biomarker quantification and data analysis are key aspects.

Considerations for the translational aspect of miRNA-based biomarkers highlight the importance of collaboration between industry, clinicians and researchers. This interdisciplinary approach enhances the understanding of the practical implications of miRNA biomarkers, facilitating their integration into clinical practice and ensuring that identified candidates are not only scientifically robust but also clinically relevant and cost-effective.

Furthermore, the intermittent nature of ring trials may not capture the dynamic nature of miRNA quantification, limiting the understanding of method robustness. miRNA research demands continuous adaptation to incorporate innovative technologies. Advancements in RNA research, such as quantification platforms, e.g., RNA sequencing or digital PCR, and data analysis methods, e.g., artificial intelligence, add complexity. As new quantification platforms and analytical methodologies emerge, ring trials may provide a framework for evaluating and validating these innovations across different laboratories.

Meticulous documentation of ring trials is imperative for advancing the transparency of scientific research. Providing a detailed account of key characteristics in research publications, including the experimental design, participant selection criteria, sample characteristics and methods employed in the trial, is crucial.

To achieve this, education and training within the scientific community are essential components. Standardization efforts should be accompanied by initiatives aimed at ensuring that personnel involved have a robust understanding of the methodological elements of ring trials.

Conclusions

Ring trials present a valuable strategy for addressing the reproducibility challenges linked to miRNA-based biomarkers. By promoting standardization, identifying sources of variability and facilitating collaboration, ring trials will contribute to the establishment of robust and reliable practices within the miRNA research community. As the field continues to evolve, the integration of ring trials into research workflows holds promise for accelerating the translation of miRNA-based biomarkers into clinical applications.

In this context, the AtheroNET COST Action (CA21153, <https://atheronet.eu/>), an international consortium aimed at enhancing the use of omics technologies in managing atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease [8], is spearheading the integration of ring trials within this domain. Specifically, the initiative is being led by Working Group 3 (Standardization and Harmonization of Research) to organize ring trials among field experts, targeting key pre-analytical and analytical challenges.

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